

Editorial

Why Studying E-Resources Usage Statistics is Essential in Academic Libraries?

From a Librarian's Viewpoint

In today's digital age, academic libraries are increasingly investing in electronic resources (e-resources) such as databases, e-journals, e-books, and other digital content. These resources offer unparalleled access to information and scholarly materials, supporting the educational and research needs of students, faculty, and researchers. However, the effective management and utilization of these resources require careful monitoring and analysis. From a librarian's viewpoint, studying e-resources usage statistics is crucial for several reasons, including optimizing resource allocation, enhancing user experience, and demonstrating the value of library services.

E-resources usage statistics refer to data on how electronic resources are accessed and utilized by library users, including metrics such as downloads, views, searches, and sessions, along with user demographics and access patterns. Studying these statistics is essential for optimizing resource allocation, justifying investments, and aligning with user needs. By analyzing usage data, librarians can identify high-performing resources, maximize cost-effectiveness, and reevaluate underutilized subscriptions, thus informing collection development and addressing gaps. This data-driven approach enhances user experience by enabling tailored services, improving accessibility, and identifying barriers. Additionally, e-resources usage statistics demonstrate a library's value in supporting teaching, learning, and research, aiding in resource management, promoting digital literacy, fostering collaboration, and driving technological advancements.

Understanding the overall importance of studying the e-resources usage statistics, the International Journal of Information Studies and Libraries (IJISL) has always promoted the publication of such research and surveys to support this awareness program. Over the years, several such studies have been published in IJISL. For instance, Jan and Ganaie (2016) found that Social Science students preferred print resources over e-resources due to low awareness and lack of orientation, despite having positive perceptions towards e-library resources. Similarly, Kannappanavar and Madhu (2016) revealed that scientists in Plantation Crops Research Institutes extensively used electronic information resources, mainly accessed from their departments and homes, though often acquired through self-study. Kashtwari (2017) showed that research scholars at the University of Kashmir exhibited high awareness and adept use of e-resources in science faculties, with library staff providing limited support. Brar et al. (2018) highlighted the awareness, access, and use of e-journals among Library and Information Science researchers through a detailed empirical approach. Saini and Kaur (2019) evaluated the usage and satisfaction levels of e-resources in DAV College Libraries, emphasizing their necessity in enhancing the quality of educational and research activities. Ranawat (2020) examined the integration of e-journals in Udaipur's higher education libraries, which significantly benefited students' academic pursuits and had a positive impact on satisfaction with ICT services. Lastly, Avhad (2023) indicated that postgraduate students at Krantiveer Vasant Naik College exhibited a growing interest in e-resources despite challenges like slow downloading, reflecting a positive trend in academic usage.

Overall, analyzing e-resources usage statistics is crucial for optimizing resource allocation, improving user experience, demonstrating value, and promoting digital literacy in academic libraries. By utilizing usage data, librarians can make informed decisions that meet user needs, support academic success, and manage digital resources effectively. Additionally, examining these statistics encourages collaboration, innovation, and continuous improvement, establishing the library as a vital and dynamic academic resource. As information and technology continue to evolve, the importance of studying e-resources usage statistics will increase, enabling libraries to adapt and thrive in the digital age.

Best Wishes

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